

THE PLACE WHERE THE MOTHER BEES ESCAPE (FERTILIZE) IN THE BEES

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Abstract. *When choosing a hiding place for queen bees, it is necessary to choose wooded areas from forests, groves, mountain foothills, and oasis zones, because such groves protect the wind and nuclei from sunlight, and conditions are created for the queen bees to fly to and from the destination. There should not be any apiaries, not even infected bees, within 5-6 km of the escape area. If there are farms engaged in breeding in the cultivation of bees, in this case, special measures should be taken to control the fertilization of many bees.*

Keywords: *forest, escape, oasis, nucleus, diseased, farms, control, fertilize, roadside, arboretum, queen bees, male bees, peaceful queens, stamp, sign of paternity, strength of family, male bees.*

Introduction: The colony of queen bees is located away from the main apiary. Nuclei and parental bee families are mainly placed in the escape area. In such places, during the meeting of the mother and male bees, there should be long-term feeding from the field, and such places should be blocked from the wind, not be on the side of the highway, and there should be no rivers, canals, and water bodies.

When choosing a hiding place for queen bees, it is necessary to choose wooded areas from forests, groves and mountain foothills, as well as oasis zones, because such groves protect the wind and nuclei far from sunlight, and conditions are created for the queen bees to fly to and from the destination. There should not be any apiaries, not even infected bees, within 5-6 km of the escape area. If there are farms engaged in breeding in the cultivation of bees, in this case, special measures should be taken to control the fertilization of many bees.

In order to increase the productivity of the bee family, it is necessary to pay special attention to the paternal families. It is necessary to have strong paternal bee families in the place where the mother bees are moved, and when the strength of the family decreases, it is necessary to give them stimulating and protein food. It should not be forgotten that on open and warm days, around 14-15 hours, the flying activity of male bees increases significantly.

Genetic traits passed on to offspring by the mother and male bees are passed on from both sides. The bee brood carries the characteristics of both sexes. In order for the male bees to be homogenous (but paternity) in their genetic traits, only male bees should be flying around the queen bees. For this, it is necessary to ensure that the bee families multiply around this area. In order to provide a colony full of male bees, it is necessary to increase the number of male bees in the family, and not the families of the father bees. It is best to place the colonies of bees in the center of the apiary and rotate the nuclei around it, rather than in the path of the bees' flight.

Methodology of the research: full click on the queen bee.

1. Stamping. In order to know the year of the queen bee and her coming and going, they have a light colored stamp on the upper part of her chest. The year of such marked queen bees can be known immediately. The year of the queen bees in all families in the apiary can be known by annual marking of the queen bees. By tagging, you can also identify the peacefully changing queen bees in the family. In breeding work, conditions are created for selection of breeding and

productive queen bees by marking. If the queen bees bred specifically for sale are labeled for their breed, they are valued at 5-10% more than other unlabeled queen bees.

Aniline dyes are used for branding the queen bees, the best colors are red, white, yellow, and blue. Such paints are prepared from a solution of nelluloid in acetone. Small hair-like brushes with a diameter of 1-1.5 mm are used for marking the queen bees. Separate brushes are used for different paints. The paint should be dripped on the breast of the queen bee in such a way that it should not damage the head and wings of the queen bee. The diameter of the stamp should not exceed 2-3 mm.

In some foreign countries, special stamps made of foil paper or thin plastic with a diameter of 2 mm are produced for marking queen bees. Such stamps are attached to the breast of the mother bee using special glues. In addition, when branding a queen bee, there is a way to cut off her wings from the upper part. To do this, the queen bee is gently removed from the chest and the tips of the wings are cut off with sharp scissors, but this method is not often used because it negatively affects the work of the fertilized queen bee.

2. Auditing. Auditing is the assessment of queen bees based on their quality characteristics, their productivity, heredity, egg-laying ability, and suitability of farm quality characteristics. Therefore, the inspection of queen bees increases the value of her breeding in beekeeping. In the implementation of these works, daily observations in the apiary, entries in the apiary journal and analyzes of zootechnical calculations are taken into account.

The purpose of inspection is to comprehensively study the qualities of breeding mother bees, to determine the aspects necessary for selection and breeding, and to make changes to it. The inspection of queen bees has its own aspects, because these works are not carried out in any apiary or farms, but only in state farms engaged in breeding work, special breeding nurseries and beekeeping associations.

Inspection of queen bees is carried out from the spring months. For this, healthy queen bees are selected, her breed identification, ability to lay eggs per day, winter resistance and many other similar qualities are studied. (Toraev O.S. and others).

3. Disqualification of queen bees. The quality of the queen bee is determined by the growth of her family. A high level of productivity of the bee family is definitely a sign of excellent, high-quality queen bees. Young quality queen bees lay eggs evenly in the cells of the frames, without mistaking them all, as a result, the closed brood in the frame is in a complete state. Old and old queen bees do not lay eggs evenly in the cells in the frame, resulting in a closed brood in the frame that looks like a wire mesh fence. Such low-quality queen bees should be quickly replaced with high-quality and fertile queen bees from breeding families. It is known from the experiments that the poor-quality, low-productivity queen bees were replaced by wool.

Replacement of queen bees is carried out according to the tune; a). When the productivity of queen bees is low regardless of their age; b). Old, aged queen bees; c). Mother bees that winter badly in the bee family; g). When the queen bee is sick or at risk of disease. The replacement of queen bees is usually carried out as a result of observations made throughout the year and records recorded in the apiary log. For this, productivity, age, quality and many other characteristics of queen bees are taken into account.

Results of the study: transfer and exchange of queen bees to the family. One of the main tasks in the field of beekeeping is the timely transfer of queen bees to the family. The strength, acid resistance, productivity and other beneficial economic characteristics of the bee family

depend on the genetic characteristics of the queen and male bees. Also, which breed the family belongs to depends on which male bees the queen has mated with. The queen's age has a great influence on the quality of her eggs and the quality of her productivity. The queen bee lives for 4-5 years, but she is very fertile only in the first and second years. After that, the process of oogenesis - the formation of germ cells - decreases in his genitals, as a result of which the production of offspring decreases sharply. In old queen bees, the function of the sperm pump is impaired, as a result, in most cases, unfertilized eggs are laid in the cells of normal bees and fertilized eggs are laid in the cells of male bees.

The age of the queen also greatly affects the migration of the bee colony. A two-year-old colony of queen bees produces 3 times more brood than a one-year-old colony. The bee family often changes their hives depending on the characteristics of the mother bees that do not have physiological value. In addition, families with young queen bees are less prone to diseases, especially varroaosis. Thus, the replacement of two-year-old queen bees with younger ones is an important technological process in beekeeping, which not only increases the strength of the bee family, but also prevents family productivity, separation of colonies, fights against varroaosis, and somewhat improves wintering results.

The transfer of queen bees to the family is carried out not only on the basis of a plan, by replacing the old queen bees, but also when the queen bees are lost for various reasons during the establishment of new colonies of bees, when they are replaced by a new breed of queen bees, when the achievements of selection science are introduced into beekeeping.

Today, in beekeeping, there are more than 50 ways to transfer and replace queen bees. For this reason, it is necessary to know the factors affecting the reception of the queen bees during the period of changing the queen bees, because different results can be obtained during the transfer of queen bees with the same method. That's why it is important to choose the right ways when changing the queen bee and transferring it to the family.

Conclusion: Factors affecting transfer of queen bees to family.

Yakovlev and Letedov (1986) studied the effects of multiple colonies and their causes on the transfer of queen bees to families.

A). Seasonal periods of honey collection. The aggression of the queen bee to the bee family has a seasonal character. The best time to transfer the queen bees to the family is the period of rapid growth of the family in the spring. With the beginning of summer, when there is less aphid in nature, there are certain changes in the transfer of queen bees to the family, because during this period, with the development of the family, they are prepared for migration, and a large number of anatomically male bees appear. It is during this period that with the increase of male bees, their aggressiveness in receiving the queen bees increases.

If the nectar is flowing well and the main honey collection season has started, the mother will be more receptive to transferring the bees to the family. At the end of the honey collection season, when the queen is replaced in the colony, aggression towards her increases. Later, aphids from the field slow down to some extent. Therefore, it is advisable to feed the bee family with a certain amount of sugar juice before and after the main honey collection when transferring the queen bees to the family. When the temperature in the apiary is low, when there is precipitation and unpleasant wind, and when there are theft attacks between families in the apiary, the queen bees are not well received by the bees.

B). Physiological condition of bees and queen bees.

A fledgling bee colony is more receptive to new queen bees than a strong colony. In such a case, the young bees who cannot fly will not have any aggression towards the newly transferred mother bees. Any colony of bees will accept fertilized queens more readily than unfertilized queens, and replacing old queens with young fertile queens also works well. This is because the bees in the colony detect the smell of the ectohormones released by young fertilized queens more quickly than those of unfertilized queens. Freshly released unfertilized queen bees are better accepted by the bee colony than older unfertilized queen bees, because such young queens move very slowly and pale in the hive frames and do not disturb the worker bees.

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